

Effects of Untreated Pharmaceutical Effluents on the Soil Physicochemical Properties

¹Nwakoby Nnamdi Enoch., ²Onuorah Samuel Chinedu., ³Thekwumere Ikechukwu Harmony.,
⁴Ejimofor Chiamaka Frances and ⁵Obiefuna Obianuju Helen

^{1,3,5}Department of Microbiology, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Uli, Anambra State, Nigeria,

²Department of Microbiology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria.

⁴Department of Biological Science, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Uli, Anambra State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

A good agricultural soil is characterized by adequate nutrients and stipulated Physicochemical properties. Most agricultural soil in Nigeria has been subjected to different kinds of pollutants resulting from anthropogenic activities, notably Untreated Pharmaceutical Effluents (UPE) which emerge as the major threatening factor to the quality of Nigerian agricultural soil. This study was undertaken to X-ray the effects of UPE on the soil Physicochemical properties. UPE samples were collected from five major pharmaceutical companies (P1, P2, P3, P4 and P5) in Anambra State, and these samples were analyzed for Physicochemical properties using instrumentation and gravimetric techniques. The Physicochemical analysis of the selected agricultural soil samples and UPE-polluted sites (25L/9m², 50L/9m² and 100L/9m²) were also determined. The study revealed that the Physicochemical parameters of the UPE were above the stipulated limits of the World Health Organization (WHO). There was reduction in the pH, increase in nitrates, sulphates, phosphates and significant ($P < 0.05$) reduction in microbial counts of UPE polluted sites, mostly in 100L/9m² sites. Therefore, this study has shown that the Physicochemical properties were significantly reduced in UPE polluted sites, mostly in 100L/9m² site.

Keywords: Effluents, Pharmaceuticals, toxicity, Physicochemical

INTRODUCTION

Pharmaceutical effluents are wastes generated during the process of drug manufacturing by pharmaceutical industries (Anjali *et al.*, 2014). When these effluents are discharged directly into the environment without proper handling and treatment, they affect both human health and the environments. Their risks to human health and the environment cannot be overemphasized. Increase in demand of pharmaceuticals in Nigeria has led to consequential increase in the amount of waste generated which most times contain recalcitrant substances that are either cytotoxic or genotoxic and sometimes both (Olaitan *et al.*, 2014).

Industrialization and man's activities have partially or totally turned our environment to dumping sites for waste materials. As a result, many water resources have been rendered unwholesome and hazardous to man and other living systems (Bakare *et al.*; 2003). The toxic substances discharged into water bodies are not only accumulated through the food chain, but may also either limit the number of species or produce dense population of micro-organisms.

In Nigeria, pollution of the surface and underground water by oil and solid wastes is widespread, thereby rendering them unsuitable for man's use. In addition, untreated wastes are either deposited on the ground or discharged into nearby natural water bodies (Bruce *et al.*, 2010).

Over the last three decades, there has been increasing global concern over the public health impacts attributed to environmental pollution, in particular, the global burden of disease. The World Health Organization estimates that about a quarter of the disease facing mankind today occur due to prolonged exposure to environmental pollution. Most of these environment-related diseases are however, not easily detected and may be acquired during childhood and manifest later in adulthood. This work was aimed to determine the effects of untreated pharmaceutical effluents on the soil physicochemical properties with specific objectives to; determine physicochemical qualities of pharmaceutical effluent, determine the physicochemical qualities of a sample of unpolluted soil and also determine the physicochemical and microbiological properties of pharmaceutical effluent polluted soil.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Physicochemical Analysis

The physicochemical analyses were carried out to determine some major parameters. The parameters analysed were: pH, electrical conductivity, salinity, alkalinity, moisture content, total suspended solids (TSS), total dissolved solids (TDS), turbidity, colour, chemical oxygen demand (COD), biological oxygen demand (BOD), total titrate acid (TTA), dissolved oxygen (DO), chloride content, nitrate content, phosphate content, lead content, copper content, sulphate content, barium content, cadmium content, iron content, manganese content, nickel content and zinc content.

Determination of pH

This was determined instrumentally by measuring directly using a pH meter. The pH meter was calibrated first using buffer solutions of 4.7 and 9.2. 1g of the sample was weighed inside beaker before dissolving with 10ml of water. The electrode of the pH meter was immersed inside the sample solution and the pH readings were measured as read directly from the screen of the meter when the point becomes steady (AOAC, 2010).

Determination of Electrical Conductivity

This was measured instrumentally using electrical conductivity meter. 20ml of the sample solution was poured inside the beaker and the electrode of the conductivity meter was immersed into the beaker. The readings were taken from the screen of the conductivity meter (AOAC, 2010).

Cyanide Determination

The hydrogen Cyanide Content was determined using the method described by Onwuka (2005). 5g of the sample was dissolved in 50ml of distilled water in a conical flask and allowed to stay overnight, and filtered after. 2ml of the filtrate was poured into a conical flask and 4mL alkaline picrate solution was added and incubated in water bath for 5 minutes for colour development (reddish brown colour) and absorbance was taken at 490nm. Also blank was prepared using 2ml of distilled water. The cyanide content was extrapolated using a cyanide standard curve.

$$\% \text{ Hydrogen Cyanide} = \frac{100 \times A_n \times C \times V_f}{W \times A_s \times V_a} \times 10^6$$

Where; A_n = Absorbance of test sample

A_s = Absorbance of standard solution

C = Concentration of standard solution

W = Weight of sample used

V_f = Total volume of extract

V_a = Volume of extract analyzed.

Determination of Total Titrable Acid

This was determined using gravimetric method described by AOAC (2010). 1g of the sample was weighed inside conical flask, then 10ml of distilled water was added. Two drops of phenolphthalein indicator was added and titrated against 0.01N NaOH solution until a persistent pink colour was observed as the end point.

$$\text{Acidity (mg/l)} = \frac{A \times M \times 50,000}{\text{Volume of Sample}}$$

Where: A = Titration Value

M = Molarity of NaOH.

Determination of Chloride

Twenty ML of the sample was transferred into a conical flask and 2 drops of potassium chromate was added to obtain a yellow colouration. 0.1M of silver nitrate solution was used to titrate the sample until a pink colour end point was obtained (AOAC, 2010).

Calculation:

$$\text{Cl (mg/l)} = \frac{\text{Volume of AgNO}_3 \text{ Used} \times M \times 35.5 \times 1000}{\text{Volume of sample.}}$$

Where M = Molarity of silver nitrate.

Determination of Calcium

Calcium content of the digested sample was determined by EDTA complexometric titration method as described by Onwuka (2005). 10ml of the sample solution was dispensed into separate conical flasks, pinches of the masking agents (potassium cyanide, potassium ferrocyanide and hydroxyl hydrochloride) were measured into the content of each flask. 20ml of ammonia buffer was added to one of the flasks to raise the pH to 10.0 while 10ml of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution was added to the other to raise the pH to 12. To the flask at pH of 10.0 (for calcium) a pinch of Erichrome dark indicator was added and titrated against 0.02N EDTA solution. The other flask at pH of 12, a reagent blank was titrated as a control. The calcium content of the samples wa calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Calcium} = \frac{100 \times E_w \times N}{W \times 100} \times \frac{V_f}{V_a}$$

Where: W = Weight of sample analyzed

Vf = Volume of extract

Va = Volume of extract used

N = Normality

Determination of Phosphorous

The phosphorous in the sample was determined by the Vanado-molybdate (yellow) spectrometry described by Onwuka (2005). 1ml extract from the sample was dispensed into a test tube. Similarly, the sample volume of standard phosphorous solution as well as water were measured into other test tubes to serve as standard and blank respectively. The contents of each tube were mixed with equal volume of the vanado-molybdate colour reagent. They were left to stand for 15 minutes at room temperature before their absorbance were measured in Jenway electronic spectrophotometer at wavelength of 420nm. Measurements were taken with the blank at zero.

Phosphorous content was obtained by the formula:

$$P \text{ (mg/100g)} = \frac{100}{W} \times \frac{A_u}{A_s} \times \frac{C}{V_a} \times V_f$$

Where: P = Phosphorous

W = Weight of sample analysed

A_u = Absorbance of the test sample

A_s = Absorbance of the standard solution

V_f = Total volume of filtrate

V_a = Volume of filtrate analysed

C = Concentration of the standard solution

Determination of Potassium and Sodium

Potassium and sodium were determined by flame photometry method as described by Onwuka (2005). The instrument (photometer) was set up according to the manufacturer's instruction. 1ml of prepared potassium and sodium standard solutions was aspirated into the machine and sprayed over the non-luminous butane gas flame. The sodium and potassium emissions (having been appropriately filtered) from the different concentrations were recorded and made into standard curve. Subsequently, the optical density emissions recorded from each of the sample were *plotted* against those in the curve, then using the curve to extrapolate the quality of sodium and potassium in the sample.

Determination of Total Dissolved Solid (TDS)

This was measured instrumentally using electrical conductivity meter by replacing the conductivity mode of the instrument with the Total Dissolved Solid mode. 20ml of the sample solution was measured into a beaker and the electrode of the instrument immersed into the solution. The readings were taken from the screen of the meter (AOAC, 2010).

RESULTS

Physiochemical properties of the pharmaceutical effluents.

The physiochemical properties of pharmaceutical effluents collected randomly from discharge points of five notable pharmaceutical companies (P1, P2, P3, P4 and P5) in Anambra state was presented in Table 1. The study revealed that the pH of the effluents collected from the five companies deviated from the stipulated WHO and FME limit and they were all acidic. Other physical properties such as colour, odour and appearance deviated from the stipulated WHO and FME limits. The total suspended solid (TSS) significantly ($P < 0.05$) deviated from the stipulated WHO and FME limits. Deviation were also recorded from the total dissolved solids (TDS) of the effluents collected from P1, P3 and P4, and these deviations were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) for P2 and P4. There were notable deviations from dissolved oxygen (DO) values of the effluents, but these were significant ($P < 0.05$) for P2 and P4. The study also recorded deviations from Biochemically Oxygen Demand (BOD) and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) of the pharmaceutical effluents. The study also revealed that P4 recorded the highest deviations, followed by P2, P3, P5 and P1 that recorded the least deviations.

Table 1: Physiochemical properties of the pharmaceutical effluents.

Parameter	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	WHO	FME
pH	5.10±0.00	5.60±0.00	5.20±0.00	4.80±0.00	5.40±0.00	6.00-9.00	6.50-8.50
Colour	LG	LB	LB	LB	LB	CL	CL
Odour	OB	OB	OB	OB	OB	OL	OL
Appearance	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC	C	C
EC(US/cm)	411.61±2.71	515.22±3.12	321.17±2.03	616.31±4.18	475.31±2.92		
TSS (mg/L)	95.12±1.22	212.76±1.33	135.19±1.57	321.54±2.14	111.27±1.86	10	10
TDS (mg/L)	422.71±1.77	741.11±1.86	644.42±1.61	891.43±2.17	413.31±1.41	500	500
DO (mg/L)	7.10±0.00	3.90±0.00	5.80±0.00	2.80±0.00	6.80±0.00	7.50	7.50
BOD (mg/L)	31.86±0.11	93.40±1.12	56.14±0.91	126.14±1.02	39.72±0.21	0	0
COD (mg/L)	75.21±0.42	167.12±1.77	137.38±1.27	193.61±1.81	86.12±0.51	0	0
Total sulphate (mg/L)	341.06±2.18	471.62±3.22	386.37±2.41	511.07±3.11	361.43±2.31	500	500
Nitrate (mg/L)	38.11±0.21	43.22±0.33	38.72±0.41	52.07±0.71	38.31±0.16	50	-
Chloride (mg/L)	73.16±0.52	91.46±0.12	87.22±0.47	111.11±0.33	72.92±0.67	250	250
Phosphate (mg/L)	0.14±0.00	0.29±0.00	0.28±0.00	0.33±0.00	0.18±0.00	-	-

LG - Light grey; LB - Light Brown; CL – Colourless; OB – Objectionable; OL – Odourless; NC – Not Clear; C – Clear; EC – Electrical Conductivity; DO – Dissolved Oxygen; BOD – Biochemical Oxygen Demand; COD – Chemical Oxygen Demand; TSS –Total Suspended Solid; TDS – Total Dissolved Soid; TS = TSS + TDS; WHO – World Health Organization; FME – Federal Ministry Of Environment.

Physiochemical qualities of unpolluted soil samples from selected designed site.

The Physiochemical properties of the garden soil samples collected from the experimented site were presented Table 3. The colour of the soil sample was brown, the conductivity, pH, sulphate, nitrate and phosphate content of the selected soil samples were determined and recorded.

Table 2: Physiochemical properties of selected garden soil sample from the experiment site

Parameters	Value
Colour	Brown
pH	6.80±0.00/10% solution
EC (US/cm ²)	608.15±2.14/ 10% solution
Sulphate (mg/L)	4.22±0.01
Nitrate (mg/L)	3.86±0.03
Phosphate (mg/L)	3.03±0.03

The study revealed that there was deviation in the physiochemical properties of the untreated pharmaceutical effluent-polluted sites as shown in Tables 3, 4 and 5. There was significant ($P<0.05$) decrease in the pH of the soil samples from month 1 to month 4, and the decreased became severe after the third month. There was increase in the electrical conductivity from month 1 to month 3, and the increase became significant ($P<0.05$) after the third month. The sulphate contents showed slight increase from month 1 to month 3, but later decreased after the third month. Also deviation occurred in the appearance of the soil samples.

Table 3: Physiochemical properties of untreated pharmaceutical effluent-polluted soil samples from 25L/9m²

Parameter	Control	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4
Colour	Brown	LB	LB	LB	LB
pH	6.80±0.00	6.10±0.00	5.70±0.00	5.10±0.00	4.80±0.00
EC (µs/cm ²)	608.15±2.14	680.50±1.33	760.40±1.89	792.12±1.43	819.56±2.14
Sulphate (mg/g)	4.22±0.01	4.28±0.01	4.32±0.03	4.35±0.01	4.38±0.01
Nitrate (mg/g)	3.86±0.03	3.98±0.01	4.05±0.01	4.06±0.01	4.08±0.03
Phosphate (mg/g)	3.03±0.03	3.04±0.01	3.06±0.01	3.06±0.01	3.07±0.01

LB – Light brown

Table 4: Physiochemical properties of untreated pharmaceutical effluent-polluted soil samples from 50 L/9m²

Parameter	Control	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4
Colour	Brown	LB	LB	LB	LB
pH	6.80±0.00	5.80±0.00	5.50±0.00	4.90±0.00	4.60±0.00
EC (µs/cm ²)	608.15±2.14	710.10±1.46	780.53±2.12	824.56±1.91	876.24±1.67
Sulphate (mg/g)	4.22±0.01	4.30±0.03	4.33±0.01	4.37±0.03	4.39±0.01
Nitrate (mg/g)	3.86±0.03	3.99±0.03	4.16±0.03	4.29±0.01	4.43±0.03
Phosphate (mg/g)	3.03±0.03	3.05±0.01	3.08±0.03	3.09±0.01	3.11±0.03

LB – Light brown

Table 5: Physiochemical properties of untreated pharmaceutical effluent-polluted soil from 100 L/9m² site

Parameter	Control	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4
Colour	Brown	LB	LB	LB	GB
pH	6.80±0.00	5.40±0.00	4.70±0.00	4.10±0.00	3.20±0.00
EC (µs/cm ²)	608.15±2.14	75.40±2.31	814.15±1.86	886.60±1.33	903.14±2.21
Sulphate (mg/g)	4.22±0.01	4.31±0.01	4.36±0.03	4.41±0.03	4.40±0.01
Nitrate (mg/g)	3.86±0.03	4.11±0.01	4.54±0.01	4.61±0.01	4.58±0.03
Phosphate (mg/g)	3.03±0.03	3.07±0.01	3.11±0.01	3.14±0.03	3.13±0.01

LB – Light brown; GB – Grayish brown

Table 5: Physiochemical properties of untreated pharmaceutical effluent-polluted soil samples from 25L/9m²

Parameter	Control	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4
Colour	Brown	LB	LB	LB	LB
pH	6.80±0.00	6.10±0.00	5.70±0.00	5.10±0.00	4.80±0.00
EC (µs/cm ²)	608.15±2.14	680.50±1.33	760.40±1.89	792.12±1.43	819.56±2.14
Sulphate (mg/g)	4.22±0.01	4.28±0.01	4.32±0.03	4.35±0.01	4.38±0.01
Nitrate (mg/g)	3.86±0.03	3.98±0.01	4.05±0.01	4.06±0.01	4.08±0.03
Phosphate (mg/g)	3.03±0.03	3.04±0.01	3.06±0.01	3.06±0.01	3.07±0.01

LB – Light brown

Table 6: Physiochemical properties of untreated pharmaceutical effluent-polluted soil samples from 50 L/9m²

Parameter	Control	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4
Colour	Brown	LB	LB	LB	LB
pH	6.80±0.00	5.80±0.00	5.50±0.00	4.90±0.00	4.60±0.00
EC (µs/cm ²)	608.15±2.14	710.10±1.46	780.53±2.12	824.56±1.91	876.24±1.67
Sulphate (mg/g)	4.22±0.01	4.30±0.03	4.33±0.01	4.37±0.03	4.39±0.01
Nitrate (mg/g)	3.86±0.03	3.99±0.03	4.16±0.03	4.29±0.01	4.43±0.03
Phosphate (mg/g)	3.03±0.03	3.05±0.01	3.08±0.03	3.09±0.01	3.11±0.03

LB – Light brown

Table 7: Physiochemical properties of untreated pharmaceutical effluent-polluted soil from 100 L/9m² site

Parameter	Control	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4
Colour	Brown	LB	LB	LB	GB
pH	6.80±0.00	5.40±0.00	4.70±0.00	4.10±0.00	3.20±0.00
EC (µs/cm ²)	608.15±2.14	75.40±2.31	814.15±1.86	886.60±1.33	903.14±2.21
Sulphate (mg/g)	4.22±0.01	4.31±0.01	4.36±0.03	4.41±0.03	4.40±0.01
Nitrate (mg/g)	3.86±0.03	4.11±0.01	4.54±0.01	4.61±0.01	4.58±0.03
Phosphate (mg/g)	3.03±0.03	3.07±0.01	3.11±0.01	3.14±0.03	3.13±0.01

LB – Light brown; GB – Grayish brown

DISCUSSION

The deviations of the physicochemical parameters of the studied untreated pharmaceutical effluents (UPE) from the stipulated limits of World Health Organization (WHO) agrees with the findings of Idris *et al.* (2013), Anjali *et al.* (2014) and Olaitan *et al.* (2014) but disagrees with Siyanbola *et al.* (2011), Kumere (2019), Pardon *et al.* (2019) and Jitesh *et al.* (2020) who reported that the physicochemical properties of UPE were within the WHO stipulated limits. But in present study, most physicochemical properties derived from the stipulated limits of WHO. The physicochemical and microbial qualities of garden soil samples collected from the experimental site were within the stipulated limits of WHO and Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). The total bacterial counts (TBC), Nitrifying bacterial counts (NBC), Phosphate solubilizing bacterial counts (LBC) were within the stipulated limits of soil enriched with nutrients that is designed for agricultural purposes as reported by many researchers (Olaitan *et al.*, 2014; Jalowiecki *et al.*, 2019; Nkoom *et al.*, 2019). The deviation of the physicochemical properties of the UPE-polluted soil recorded in the present study agrees with the findings of Ekhaise and Anyansi (2005), Carter *et al.* (2015), Kumar *et al.* (2019), Klodesova *et al.* (2016) and Less *et al.* (2016) but deviated from the reports of Kumere (2019) and Hurtado *et al.* (2017) who only focused on the treatment strategies, human usage and heavy metal constituents of pharmaceutical effluents-polluted soil. The deviations in the physicochemical properties of the soil samples could be attributed to the acidic nature of the UPE, presence of dissolved and suspended pollutants that could alter the soil pH and other physicochemical properties.

CONCLUSION

Many pharmaceutical industries produce toxic effluents from their production operation. The waste water generated from these industries possess solids, biodegradable and non-biodegradable organic compounds. Pharmaceutical effluents propose basic information about the reliability of the aquatic habitat in rivers and streams into which they are discharged. The physicochemical analysis of the effluents point towards the industries, that they obey the standard guidelines of Federal Environmental Protection Agency.

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